

INFLUENCE OF METALLIC SALTS ON THE SIZE-FREQUENCY OF GELATIN-PROTECTED EMULSIONS

BY C. S. NARWANI AND T. C. PARAKH

The size-frequency of the gelatin-protected emulsions has been measured from the time-accumulation curves, obtained from the change in transparency of cream-zone of transparent emulsions with time, by means of a photo-electric cell. The size-frequency curves have been plotted for the transparent emulsions of amyl acetate in 1% gelatin-water-glycerine sol in presence of 1.5 millimoles of (i) KCl, (ii) KBr, (iii) KSCN, (iv) KI, (v) K_2SO_4 . The changes in viscosities of the continuous phase and the interfacial tension between the continuous and the disperse phase with the addition of the above-mentioned salts have been studied experimentally and the influence of these changes compared with those in the size-frequency of particles of the emulsions. The amount of the disperse phase with varying radii as well as the size-frequency decrease in the order: $K_2SO_4 > KCl > KBr$, while it increases slightly on addition of KI and KSCN, the former being more effective than the latter; the change in interfacial tension follows the same order.

Clowes (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1916, 20, 407) observed that the addition of small amounts of NaCl up to 0.1M to the emulsions of olive oil in dilute soap solutions increased their stability due to the adsorption of Cl⁻ ions in excess of Na⁺ ions on the soap particles, while in the case of higher concentrations, the stabilising film was precipitated and the emulsion broke. Carpenter (*ibid.*, 1927, 31, 1873) and Carpenter and Kucerol (*ibid.*, 1931, 35, 2619) working on the influence of salts on the optical rotation of gelatin, found that salts produced lowering of optical activity, the magnitude of the effect decreasing in the order: $KCl < KBr < KNO_3 < KClO_3 < KI < KSCN$; this order compares well with that of Bancroft (*ibid.*, 1915, 19, 349) for adsorption of anions by albumin. The adsorption of various neutral salts on isoelectric gelatin has been studied by Docking and Heymann (*ibid.*, 1939, 43, 513) and the order obtained for potassium salts is $SO_4 < Cl < NO_3 < Br < I < CNS$. The object of the present work is to ascertain if there is a change in the size of the particles as studied from size-frequency curves of transparent emulsions of amyl acetate in gelatin sols, treated with small quantities of KCl, KBr, KI, K_2SO_4 and KSCN. For obtaining the size-frequency curves according to the method of Kraemer and Stamm (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1924, 46, 2709), the time-accumulation curves have been plotted by measuring the change in transparency of cream-zone of transparent emulsion by a photo-electric cell. Further, it has been examined if the change in stability of such emulsions, determined from the stand-point of viscosity and interfacial tension, tallies with the change in size-frequency of the particles.

EXPERIMENTAL

A transparent gelatin-protected emulsion was obtained by dispersing amyl acetate in the mixture of 57 c.c. of gelatin-water sol and 43 c.c. of glycerine

(dehydrated), the refractive indices of both the phases being equal at 35°. The emulsion (50%), prepared by gradual addition of the disperse phase and shaking in the mechanical shaker and homogenised under high pressure, was used in every experiment. The salt, whose influence was to be studied, was dissolved in the continuous phase before preparing the emulsion.

A definite volume of the emulsion was introduced into a well dried, rectangular, white glass bottle of plane parallel sides, having dimensions, 4" × 2.5" × 1" and an air-tight cork, and was placed in an air-thermostat at 35° ± 0.20 on a stable stand with sliding arrangement, in horizontal as well as in vertical direction, opposite a fixed metallic slit (1.5" × 0.5") in the back wall of the thermostat. Just behind the slit was an electric lamp (12 volts, 75 watts) with a convex lens to give a parallel beam of light; the same voltage (12 volts) was always supplied from a slide wire potentiometer, connected to a storage battery. Between the slit and the emulsion bottle was placed an air-tight rectangular bottle, containing 1N-CuSO₄ solution to absorb heat rays and ultraviolet rays as suggested by Morse (*Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1936, 32, 941). In close contact with the emulsion bottle was placed a photo-electric cell (potassium) fitted up in a wooden box with a thin glass window. The light from the slit, after passing through the CuSO₄ solution and the upper portion of the cream-zone of the emulsion, fell on the photo-electric cell. A similar glass bottle having the same dimensions and containing dehydrated glycerine was every now and then placed in the same position as the emulsion bottle, to test the constancy of the intensity of light. The change in the electric current, produced in the photo-electric cell, was measured by means of a D'Arsonval mirror galvanometer. On allowing the transparent emulsion to stand, the cream-zone opposite the slit became more and more opaque owing to the increase of concentration of the disperse phase. The changes in current with time, as shown in Table I, in terms of scale divisions, being proportional to those in opacity, plotted against time, give the accumulation curve.

The size-frequency curves are obtained by plotting radius of the particles against d_s/d_r , obtained from the time-accumulation curve according to the method of Kraemer and Stamm (*loc. cit.*); the radius of the particle (r) is calculated from Stokes law,

$$r = \sqrt{\frac{9h\eta}{2(S_p - S_d)gt}}$$

where h = height of the cream-zone, η = viscosity of the continuous phase at 35°, S_d denotes density of the disperse phase, S_p , the density of the continuous phase, g , the gravity constant, and t , time in minutes at which the reading of the mirror galvanometer was taken; d_s is the distance between the ordinate intercepts of the two successive tangents to the time-accumulation curve, d_r is the difference between the radii, calculated at the two corresponding successive times. The area, bounded by any portion of the size-frequency curve and the abscissa, corresponds to the actual weight of the disperse phase with particles whose radii vary between the values represented by the bounding abscissa. The size-frequency curves for the

emulsions containing various quantities of KCl and KI, are shown in Figs. 1 and 2 respectively; the bounded area decreases with increase in concentration of KCl, KBr and K_2SO_4 ; in case of KI and KSCN there is a slight increase in area, bounded by the size-frequency curves, with the increase in concentration of the salt. The viscosities of the continuous phases, determined by Ostwald's viscometer, interfacial tensions between the two phases of the emulsions, determined by stalagmometer (drop-weight method) and the maxima of the size-frequency curves in presence of various quantities of different salts are shown in Table II.

FIG. 1.

Size-frequency curve (KCl)

TABLE I

5 Millimoles of salt were added to 1% gelatin sol. 50% transparent emulsion of amyl acetate prepared and allowed to cream. The decrease in deflection of the mirror galvanometer in terms of scale divisions with time is shown below against each salt.

Time.	No salt added.	K ₂ SO ₄ .	KCl.	KBr.	KSCN.	KI.
30 min.	06	03	03	03	11	12
60	09	05	05	05	18	18
90	12	06	07	07	21	22
120	15	07	08	08	24	24
150	17	08	09	10	25	26
180	20	09	10	11	26	27
240	22	11	12	13	28	29
300	24	12	14	15	29	31
360	25	13	15	16	30	31.75
420	26	14	16	17	31	32
540	27	15	17	18	32	33
1320	28	16	20	20	34	34
1440	28	16	20	20	34	34

TABLE II

Salt added to 100 c.c. of 1% gelatin sol.	Relative viscosity.	Interfacial tension.	Maxima of S.F. curve.	Pot. chloride.			Pot. bromide.		
				Relative viscosity.	Interfacial tension.	Maxima of S.F. curve.	Relative viscosity.	Interfacial tension.	Maxima of S.F. curve.
0 mM.	5.879	17.15	1.38						
1	6.136	17.13	0.70	5.903	17.10	0.85	5.912	17.13	0.95
2	6.181	17.02	0.63	5.933	17.05	0.71	5.943	17.10	0.82
3	6.220	16.94	0.50	5.960	17.01	0.57	5.968	17.06	0.65
4	6.276	16.85	0.40	5.990	16.98	0.43	6.005	17.01	0.54
5	6.327	16.79	0.34	6.030	16.94	0.35	6.043	16.95	0.48
		Pot. iodide.						KSCN.	
1 mM.	5.975	17.26	1.40				5.987	17.22	1.39
2	6.001	17.39	1.41				6.009	17.30	1.38
3	6.029	17.52	1.43				6.017	17.39	1.40
4	6.077	17.51	1.45				6.036	17.47	1.41
5	6.049	17.74	1.47				6.039	17.57	1.42

DISCUSSION

Table I shows that the rate of creaming, as measured by the increase in opacity due to arrival of more disperse phase in the cream-zone, decreases on addition of K₂SO₄, KCl, and KBr, while it increases on addition of KSCN and KI. Since

there is a gradual increase in opacity and it is very small within the interval between 540 and 1320 minutes. there must be no change in size of the particle of the previously formed cream-zone with time.

FIG. 2.
Six-frequency curve (KI)

It is seen from Fig. 1 that on addition of KCl to the gelatin-protected emulsion, there is a decrease in the maxima as well as in the total area bounded by the size-frequency curves. Table II shows that the viscosity of the continuous phase goes on increasing and interfacial tension between the continuous and disperse phase goes on decreasing with the addition of K_2SO_4 , KCl and KBr. Since the changes in the interfacial tension can directly determine the changes in stability of the emulsions, it is concluded from the above-mentioned observation that the changes in the total area bounded by the size-frequency curves should give us an idea about the stability of the emulsions. Bearing this in mind it is concluded from these size-frequency curves that additions of small amounts of K_2SO_4 , KCl or KBr increases the stability of the gelatin-protected emulsion in the order : $K_2SO_4 > KCl > KBr$.

In case of KI (Fig. 2) and KSCN, there is a slight but regular increase in the maxima (refer to Table II) as well as in the total area bounded by the size-frequency curves with increase in the concentration. The interfacial tension also increases with the increase in concentration. So addition of small amount of KI and KSCN decreases the stability in the order : $KI > KSCN$.

The general observation is that the influence of addition of small amounts of the salts on the size-frequency of the particles as well as the stability of the gelatin-protected emulsion follows rigidly the same order as that on changes in interfacial tension.

CHEMICAL LABORATORY,
D. J. SIND COLLEGE, KARACHI (SIND).

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